

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks
hash://md5/15898844ff545374712510dfb90e7cd8

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
review@globalbioticinteractions.org
<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks/issues>

2026-01-28

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks, has fingerprint hash://md5/15898844ff545374712510dfb90e7cd8, is 16.8KiB in size and contains 213,244 interactions with 8 unique types of associations (e.g., hasHost) between 21,096 primary taxa (e.g., Trichogramma) and 23,244 associated taxa (e.g., Citrus). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

Contents

Introduction	2
Data Review and Archive	2
Methods	2
Results	4
Files	4
Archived Dataset	14
Biotic Interactions	14

Interaction Networks	20
Geospatial Distribution	20
Taxonomic Alignment	20
Additional Reviews	25
GloBI Review Badge	26
GloBI Index Badge	29
Discussion	29
Acknowledgements	30
Author contributions	30
References	30

Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Poelen, J. H. (2024). A biodiversity dataset graph: Biological Associations in TaxonWorks hash://sha256/e4a47c067d6c125da60c9a1b92b5eecdea539cb8666cd3aed99db347ae5 hash://md5/686007de79cc2a49ab23fd3debe56e3f [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11151783> <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks/> 2026-01-24T06:14:51.698Z hash://md5/15898844ff545374712510dfb90e7cd8

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks/> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.1
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 16.8KiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](https://github.com/Check-Data). See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/taxonworks`, has fingerprint hash://md5/15898844ff545374712510dfb90e7cd8, is 16.8KiB in size and contains 213,244 interactions with 8 unique types of associations (e.g., `hasHost`) between 21,096 primary taxa (e.g., `Trichogramma`) and 23,244 associated taxa (e.g., `Citrus`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Neuroterus hakonensis	interactsWith	Quercus	(article?) {213218, author = {Monzen, Kota}, journal = {Annual Report of the Gakugei Faculty of the Iwate University}, pages = {24-38}, title = {Revision of the Japanese gall wasps with the descriptions of new genus, subgenus, species and subspecies (II). Cynipidae (Cynipinae) Hymenoptera.}, volume = {6}, year = {1954} }
Neuroterus haasi	interactsWith	Lithocarpus elegans	(article?) {213146, author = {Kieffer, J.J.}, journal = {Bulletin de la Société d'Histoire Naturelle de Metz}, number = {11}, pages = {59-66.}, title = {Description de quelques Cynipides exotiques dont l'un forme un genre nouveau.}, volume = {2}, year = {1904} }

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Neuroterus haasi	interactsWith	Lithocarpus elegans	(book?) {212941, address = {Berlin}, author = {Dalla Torre, Karl Wilhelm von and Kieffer, J.J.}, publisher = {R. Friedländer und Sohn}, title = {Cynipidae}, year = {1910}, url = {https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/bibliography}, doi = {10.5962/bhl.title.1077}}

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Dryocosmus testisimilis	interactsWith	Castanopsis uraiana	(article?) {212997, author = {Melika, George and Tang, Chang-Ti and Nicholls, James A. and Yang, Man-Miao and Stone, Graham N.}, journal = {ISRN Zoology}, month = {may}, pages = {1-17}, title = {Four New Species of Dryocosmus gallwasps from Taiwan (Hymenoptera: Cynipidae: Cynipini)}, volume = {2011}, year = {2011}, url = { https://www.hindawi.com/journals/isrn/2011/7 abstract = {Four new species of oak gallwasps of the genus Dryocosmus : D. pentagonalis , D. triangularis , D. carlesiae , and D. testisimilis are described from Taiwan. They induce galls on one species of Castanopsis and one species of Lithocarpus (Fagaceae). Data on the diagnosis, distribution, and biology of the four new species is given. A key for Dryocosmus species identification of Taiwan is provided. Final comments discuss the polyphyletic

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
hasHost	121895
interactsWith	48080
eats	30920
parasitoidOf	10992
hasParasitoid	1298
mutualistOf	39
hasPathogen	12
preyedUponBy	8

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Trichogramma	1811
Philaenus spumarius	1310
Encarsia formosa	1307
Trichogramma minutum	1141
Tetrastichus	1136
Trichogramma evanescens	997
Trichogramma chilonis	897
Trichogramma pretiosum	864
Dibrachys cavus	762
Eurytoma	713
Eupelmus urozonus	643
Coccophagus lycimnia	609
Sympiesis sericeicornis	587
Trichogramma dendrolimi	573
Burkseus vittatus	558
Aphytis melinus	483
Leptomastix dactylopii	460
Diglyphus isaea	459
Chrysocharis pentheus	445

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Citrus	2075
Poaceae	1556
Quercus	1341
Salix	1055
Saissetia oleae	968
Trialeurodes vaporariorum	921
Aonidiella aurantii	915
Bemisia tabaci	854
Saccharum officinarum	797
Carex	772
Musca domestica	760
Root	730
Zea mays	719
Planococcus citri	704
Phyllocnistis citrella	703
Coccus hesperidum	696
Malus pumila	689
Oryza sativa	652
Medicago sativa	605

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Encarsia formosa	hasHost	Trialeurodes vaporariorum	592
Aphytis melinus	hasHost	Aonidiella aurantii	187
Encarsia formosa	interactsWith	Lycopersicon esculentum	176
Aphelinus mali	hasHost	Eriosoma lanigerum	132
Muscidifurax raptor	hasHost	Musca domestica	128
Encarsia perniciosi	hasHost	Quadraspidiotus perniciosus	127
Leptomastix dactylopii	hasHost	Planococcus citri	126
Eretmocerus mundus	hasHost	Bemisia tabaci	124
Comperiella bifasciata	hasHost	Aonidiella aurantii	115
Brachymeria intermedia	hasHost	Lymantria dispar	110
Epidinocarsis lopezi	hasHost	Phenacoccus manihoti	105
Aphytis lingnanensis	hasHost	Aonidiella aurantii	104
Oomyzus sokolowskii	hasHost	Plutella xylostella	104
Spalangia cameroni	hasHost	Musca domestica	94
Trichogramma evanescens	hasHost	Ostrinia nubilalis	93

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Encarsia formosa	hasHost	Bemisia tabaci	90
Metaphycus helvolus	hasHost	Saissetia oleae	83
Spalangia endius	hasHost	Musca domestica	81
Cales noacki	hasHost	Aleurothrixus floccosus	81

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at [indexed-interactions.gpkg](#) for point data and [indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg](#) for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at [GloBI website](#), by opening a [GitHub issue](#), or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the [GloBI website](#).

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Tanacetum vulgare siculum	NONE	col	Tanacetum vulgare siculum
Serjania glabrata	SYNONYM_OF	col	Serjania membranacea
Serjania glabrata	SYNONYM_OF	col	Serjania mucronulata

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Serjania glabrata	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Serjania glabrata

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	9269
col	class	3
col	family	233
col	form	1
col	genus	3038
col	infraspecific name	30
col	kingdom	1
col	order	11
col	phylum	1
col	section	1
col	species	27576
col	subfamily	2
col	subgenus	186
col	subspecies	663
col	subtribe	1
col	superfamily	6
col	tribe	4
col	variety	147
discoverlife	NA	40454
discoverlife	species	167
gbif	NA	5544
gbif	class	3
gbif	family	248
gbif	form	5
gbif	genus	3369
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	11
gbif	phylum	1
gbif	species	30916
gbif	subspecies	865
gbif	variety	223
itis	NA	31381
itis	class	3
itis	division	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	family	229
itis	form	1
itis	genus	1724
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	12
itis	phylum	1
itis	species	7084
itis	subclass	1
itis	subfamily	8
itis	subgenus	3
itis	subspecies	119
itis	superfamily	5
itis	superorder	1
itis	variety	65
mdd	NA	40621
ncbi	NA	24424
ncbi	clade	3
ncbi	class	2
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	237
ncbi	genus	2751
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	11
ncbi	section	2
ncbi	species	13026
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	12
ncbi	subgenus	42
ncbi	subspecies	82
ncbi	superfamily	5
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	2
ncbi	varietas	46
pbdb	NA	39122
pbdb	class	4
pbdb	family	230
pbdb	genus	926
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	infraorder	1
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	11
pbdb	phylum	1
pbdb	species	310
pbdb	subfamily	8

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	subgenus	1
pbdb	superfamily	5
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	2
tpt	NA	40536
tpt	genus	12
tpt	species	73
wfo	NA	33111
wfo	family	68
wfo	form	1
wfo	genus	1100
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	6133
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	242
wfo	variety	100
worms	NA	37839
worms	class	2
worms	family	174
worms	genus	926
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	11
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	1646
worms	subclass	1
worms	subspecies	48
worms	superfamily	1
worms	variety	18

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	9600
col	SYNONYM_OF	13526
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	31847

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
discoverlife	NONE	46563
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	139
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	60
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	12
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	18333
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	37875
gbif	NONE	5696
itis	NONE	34587
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	10743
itis	SYNONYM_OF	1795
mdd	NONE	46726
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6
ncbi	NONE	25805
ncbi	SAME_AS	19432
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	1684
pbdb	NONE	43765
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2936
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	136
tpt	NONE	46644
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	96
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	13
wfo	NONE	37095
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7919
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	3269
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1187
worms	NONE	42888
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3744
worms	SYNONYM_OF	854

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T03:10:54Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/55] and name: [Parasitoid of]
2026-01-28T03:10:54Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/55] and name: [Parasitoid of]
2026-01-28T03:10:54Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/49] and name: [Possible parasitoid of]

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T03:10:54Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/51] and name: [Parasitoid (pupa-pupa) of]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/62] and name: [adult feeds on / eaten by adult]	9
found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/46] and name: [Compared with]	8
found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/55] and name: [Parasitoid of]	7
found unsupported interaction type with id: [gid://taxon-works/BiologicalRelationship/5] and name: [vector for / has vector]	7

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-28) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

References

- Elliott, Michael, Jorrit Poelen, Icaro Alzuru, Emilio Berti, and partha04patel. 2025. “Bio-Guoda/Preston: 0.10.5.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14662206>.
- ICZN. 1999. “International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.” The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London, UK. <https://www.iczn.org/the-code/the-code-online/>.
- Kuhn, Tobias, and Michel Dumontier. 2014. “Trusty URIs: Verifiable, Immutable, and Permanent Digital Artifacts for Linked Data.” In *The Semantic Web: Trends and Challenges*, edited by Valentina Presutti, Claudia d’Amato, Fabien Gandon, Mathieu d’Aquin, Steffen Staab, and Anna Tordai, 395–410. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Kuhn, Tobias, Jorrit Poelen, and Katrin Leinweber. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Elton: 0.15.1.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14927734>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H. (ed.). 2024. “Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources Hash://Sha256/ B60c0d25a16ae77b24305782017b1a270b79b5d1746f832650 F2027ba536e276 Hash://Md5/17f1363a277ee0e4ecaf1b91c665e47e.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12695629>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H., James D. Simons, and Chris J. Mungall. 2014. “Global Biotic Interactions: An Open Infrastructure to Share and Analyze Species-Interaction Datasets.” *Ecological Informatics* 24 (November): 148–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>.
- Poelen, Jorrit, Katja Seltmann, and Daniel Mietchen. 2024. “Globalbioticinteractions/Globinizer: 0.4.0.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10647565>.
- Salim, José Augusto, and Jorrit Poelen. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Nomer: 0.5.15.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893840>.
- Trekels, Maarten, Debora Pignatari Drucker, José Augusto Salim, Jeff Ollerton, Jorrit Poelen, Filipi Miranda Soares, Max Rünzel, Muo Kasina,

- Quentin Groom, and Mariano Devoto. 2023. “WorldFAIR Project (D10.1) Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176978>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.